

A MODIFICATION OF THE GUARESCHI PYRIDINE SYNTHESIS. PART II.

NIRMALANANDA PALIT.

In Part I of this work (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 219) it was shown that under the influence of diethylamine, cyanoacetamide adds to ethyl benzylideneacetoacetate to form a ring compound (I) which presumably is the primary reaction preceding the formation of pyridines by Guareschi's method.

This intermediate compound was found to be uncommonly stable and the reactivity of the amido hydrogen atom, which is responsible for the ring closure by tautomerisation, was attributed to its position between two carbonyl groups. To test this view cyanoacetamide was replaced by the dinitriles of Meyer (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1908, **II**, 591) which can react in both the forms (II) and (III). The reaction would be parallel to one already studied by Meyer (*loc. cit.*) in which the dinitrile was condensed with an arylideneacetophenone in presence of sodium ethoxide.

Gastaldi (*Gazzetta*, 1922, 52, 169, 305) has thrown considerable doubt upon the constitution of these products. He prepared 2:4-diphenyl-6-methylpyridine (V) from the corresponding pyryllium salt and found it to be different from the product obtained by Meyer by hydrolysis of IV ($\text{Ar} = \text{Ph}; \text{R} = \text{Me}$) followed by removal of carbon dioxide. The problem was, therefore, taken up in more detail to be described in a separate communication the result of which indicates that Meyer's mode of representing the reaction is not incorrect. If that is so, benzylideneacetoacetic ester would be expected to behave in an analogous way, but sodium ethoxide failed to bring about any condensation at the room temperature and if warmed the unsaturated keto-ester was decomposed. With diethylamine, however, the condensation has been effected and a product ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_6$), m.p. 152° , is obtained and this has been identified to be benzylidenebis-acetoacetic ester whichever dinitrile is used. It shows that the dinitrile does not take part in the reaction at all. A decomposing influence of organic bases on the olefine keto-ester of a different nature has been previously recorded by Ruhemann (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 374).

Several attempts to bring about the desired reaction failed with different condensing agents and at last Kohler and Souther's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 2903) using sodium methoxide seemed to prove more fruitful. The product in every case is a sticky semisolid complex mixture which does not solidify even on prolonged standing in ice and is difficult to purify. Thus with benzoacetodinitrile (II, $\text{R} = \text{Ph}$) the product is a mixture of the pyridine (VI) and the dihydropyridine (VII) obtained previously by Meyer (*loc. cit.*).

(VI)

(VII)

No trace of a compound of intermediate aldol structure could be isolated. This is in harmony with the view suggested above.

In the above condensations, benzylidene cyanoacetic ester has also been used which is stable towards sodium ethoxide and consequently gives much better yields of pure products.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

Reactions with Ethyl Benzylideneacetoacetate.

(a) *With β -Amino- β -phenylacrylonitrile: Formation of 3:5-Dicyano-2:4:6-triphenyldihydropyridine and 5-Cyano-3-carbethoxy-2-methyl-4:6-diphenylpyridine.*—A methyl alcoholic solution of the dinitrile and the ester was treated with a few drops of methyl alcoholic sodium methoxide to give a distinct alkaline reaction. The reaction was not complete even on keeping for more than a fortnight. A subsequent heating on a water-bath facilitated the reaction. If heating was done earlier the decomposition products increased at the sacrifice of the pyridine. However in each case the alcohol on evaporation left a sticky semisolid. A solution of it in the minimum quantity of glacial acetic acid deposited on cooling a very small quantity of a pale greenish crystalline powder, m.p. 268°. (Found: C, 83.4; H, 5.0; N, 11.8. $C_{25}H_{17}N_3$ requires C, 83.2; H, 4.7; N, 11.7 per cent). The mother liquor on evaporation gave the same non-crystallisable sticky mass. After boiling for a few minutes with dilute hydrochloric acid, the extract on cooling gave white needles of the cyanoketone produced by hydrolysis of the iminonitrile. It crystallised from benzene, m.p. 189°. (Found: C, 76.92; H, 5.6; N, 8.43. $C_{22}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires C, 77.19; H, 5.29; N, 8.19 per cent).

(b) *With β -Amino- β -p-tolylacrylonitrile.*—The sticky mass obtained by evaporating the condensation mixture was boiled with dilute hydrochloric acid. The solid obtained crystallised from acetone in large plates, m.p. 189°. (Found: C, 77.78; H, 5.9; N, 7.8. $C_{23}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires C, 77.52; H, 5.6; N, 7.86 per cent).

(c) *With β -Amino-p-anisylacrylonitrile.*—The solid obtained by boiling with dilute hydrochloric acid was twice crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 190-92°, after shrinking at 187°. (Found: C, 73.92; H, 5.63; N, 7.8. $C_{24}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 74.19; H, 5.38; N, 7.51 per cent).

Reaction with Ethyl Benzylidenecyanacetate.

(a) *With β -Amino- β -phenylacrylonitrile: Formation of Diethylammonium salt of 3:5-Dicyano-2-kefo-4:6-diphenylpiperidine (cf. part I).*—0.1 Mole of each were dissolved in absolute alcohol and a few drops of diethylamine added. Next day a crystalline deposit was obtained. More of diethylamine was added till its smell persisted. The colourless crystals were

filtered after two days (1.5 g.), and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 208-10°. Boiling acetic anhydride gave the same pyridone as below. (Found: C, 74.37; H, 6.19; N, 15.45. $C_{23}H_{22}ON_4$ requires C, 74.59; H, 5.94; N, 15.13 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the above Compound: Formation of 3:5-Dicyano-4:6-diphenyl- $\Delta^{3,0}$ -dihydro-2-pyridone.—With dilute caustic soda strong ammoniacal smell was given out in the cold and when heated the evolution of the gas was copious. Nessler's reagent was unaffected by it. The reaction was quickly over. The residue crystallised from a large volume of alcohol as a voluminous mass, m. p. 250-51°. (Found: C, 76.45; H, 4.10; N, 14.44. $C_{19}H_{11}ON_3$ requires C, 76.76; H, 3.70; N, 14.14 per cent).

(b) *With β -Amino- β -p-tolylacrylonitrile: Formation of 3:5-Dicyano-4-phenyl-6-tolyl- $\Delta^{3,0}$ -dihydro-2-pyridone (cf. part I).*—The dinitrile (1.6 g.) was added to absolute alcohol in which sodium (0.23 g.) was added. On adding the unsaturated ester (2 g.) to the suspended nitrile, the colour deepened to brownish yellow and quickly the whole went into solution. It was boiled under reflux on a water-bath for two hours, the alcohol evaporated and the residual jelly treated with water. A white precipitate was obtained, which crystallised from glacial acetic acid, yield quantitative, m. p. 293°. (Found: C, 76.91; H, 4.52; N, 13.65. $C_{20}H_{13}ON_3$ requires C, 77.17; H, 4.18; N, 13.5 per cent).

(c) *With β -Amino-p-anisylacrylonitrile.*—The product crystallised from a large volume of acetone or glacial acetic acid as yellow mesh of needles, m. p. 296°. (Found: C, 73.10; H, 4.31; N, 13.0. $C_{20}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires C, 73.39; H, 4.0; N, 12.78 per cent).